

COVINFORM

CORONAVIRUS VULNERABILITIES AND INFORMATION DYNAMICS RESEARCH AND MODELLING

D7.6 Research design: Communication and information – updated M29

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

Project

Acronym	COVINFORM
Title	COronavirus Vulnerabilities and INFOrmation dynamics Research and Modelling
Coordinator	SYNYO GmbH
Reference	101016247
Type	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Programme	HORIZON 2020
Topic	SC1-PHE-CORONAVIRUS-2020-2C Behavioural, social and economic impacts of the outbreak response
Start	01 November 2020
Duration	36 months
Website	https://covinform.eu
Consortium	<p>SYNYO GmbH (SYNYO), Austria</p> <p>Magen David Adom in Israel (MDA), Israel</p> <p>Samur Proteccion Civil (SAMUR), Spain</p> <p>Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC), Italy</p> <p>SINUS Markt- und Sozialforschung GmbH (SINUS), Germany</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI UK), UK</p> <p>Trilateral Research LTD (TRI IE), Ireland</p> <p>Kentro Meleton Asfaleias – Center for Security Studies (KEMEA), Greece</p> <p>Factor Social Consultoria em Psicossociologia e Ambiente LDA (FS), Portugal</p> <p>Austrian Red Cross (AUTRC), Austria</p> <p>Media Diversity Institute (MDI), UK</p> <p>Societatea Națională de Cruce Rosie Din România – Romanian Red Cross (SNCRR), Romania</p> <p>University of Antwerp (UANTWERPEN), Belgium</p> <p>Sapienza University of Rome (SAPIENZA), Italy</p> <p>University Rey Juan Carlos (URJC), Spain</p> <p>Swansea University (SU), UK</p> <p>Gotenborg University (UGOT), Sweden</p>

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 101016247.

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Deliverable

Number	D7.6
Title	Research design: Communication and information – updated M29
Lead beneficiary	TRI
Work package	WP7
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Nature	Report (RE)
Due date	31.03.2023
Submission date	30.03.2023
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Document history

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	26.01.2023	First version of the deliverable, Zainab Mehdi
0.2	10.02.2023	Internal review, Niamh Aspell
0.3	10.02.2023	Updates following review, Zainab Mehdi
0.4	14.02.2023	Internal review, Niamh Aspell
0.5	21.02.2023	Updates following review, Zainab Mehdi
0.6	24.02.2023	Internal review, Niamh Aspell
0.7	24.02.2023	Updates following review, Zainab Mehdi
0.8	01.03.2023	Internal review, edits and feedback, Niamh Aspell and Susan Anson
0.9	07.03.2023	Final TRI review and edits before project review by UGOT
0.10	14.03.2023	UGOT provide feedback
0.11	21.03.2023	Internal review received, Niamh Aspell and Susan Anson
0.12	22.03.2023	Updates following review, Zainab Mehdi
0.13	23.03.2023	Deliverable sent to SYNNO for review
0.14	27.03.2023	Review received, Zainab Mehdi
0.15	30.03.2023	Deliverable submitted

Executive Summary

The EU-funded COVINFORM project employs intersectionality theory and complex systems analysis to examine COVID-19 responses at government (WP4), public health (WP5), community (WP6), and information and communication levels (WP7). The project includes empirical research and community-based case studies to assess responses to COVID-19. COVINFORM draws on cross-disciplinary approaches (social epidemiology, the sociology of migration, philosophy, etc.) to investigate different aspects of vulnerability in the context of the pandemic. Based on the project findings, the consortium will develop an online portal and visual toolkit for stakeholders in government, public health, and civil society integrating data streams, indices and indicators, maps, risk assessment models, primary research and case study findings, and empirically grounded policy guidance.

This report relates to Work Package (WP) 7 of the project which focuses on evaluating inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation. Key objectives of WP7 include:

- Reviewing and describing communication strategies and practices of governments and public health authorities on a national, regional and local level
- Conducting primary empirical research
- Analysing measures and tools for the prevention of misinformation, disinformation, malinformation, ‘fake news’ and conspiracy theories, exploring the impact of misinformation and digital communication on mental health and well-being of different groups, representation and justice in media specifically in connection with threat perceptions, prejudice, and discrimination
- Synthesising research findings on governmental responses and impacts and preparing recommendations and other inputs for WP8.

This report is an update of deliverable 7.2 ‘Research design: Communication and information’ submitted in M7 (May 2021). The research design presented in D7.2 provided the framework and research design for the empirical research with relevant stakeholders on the topic of inclusive COVID-19 information for behaviour change and addressing misinformation. In addition, the deliverable briefly introduced the analysis methods that will be used to analyse the data collated through both desk-based research and primary empirical research. This deliverable, D7.6 Research design: Communication and information – update M29, provides an update of changes that have been made to the empirical research design and methodology presented in D7.2.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Term	Description
WP	Work Package
SES	Socio-ecological system
DoA	Description of Action

1 Introduction

As described in the DoA and D7.2, the objectives of WP7 are:

- 1) To review and describe communication strategies and practices of government and public health authorities on a national level in the 10 project target countries, as well as on a regional/local level in selected sub-national research sites, including strategies to influence behaviour change, and a detailed analysis of factors influencing communication practices;
- 2) To carry out primary empirical research among Governmental Stakeholders and Policy Experts in 10 sub-national research sites.
- 3) To perform an in-depth analysis of measures and tools for the prevention of misinformation (unintentionally false or misleading information), disinformation (false information purposely spread) (Lazer et al., 2018), malinformation (information based in reality but used to inflict harm) (Carmi et al., 2020), 'fake news' and conspiracy theories; the impact of misinformation and digital communication on mental health and well-being of different groups; and representation and justice in the media in connection with threat perceptions, prejudice, and discrimination;
- 4) To synthesise research findings on governmental responses and impacts and prepare recommendations and other inputs for WP8

Specifically, this deliverable is an update of D7.2, COVINFORM's first report on the research design for WP7. The predominant focus of this report is to provide an update of the changes that have occurred since the submission of D7.2 until now, along with justifications for the changes made.

2 Overview of empirical research

The COVINFORM project addresses the following top-level research questions,

RQ1: How and under which conditions were COVID-19 responses drafted, implemented and experienced?

RQ2: How and in which ways was vulnerability considered in COVID-19 response?

RQ3: What were the lived experiences of the pandemic and its response within certain vulnerable groups?

RQ4: What were the different kinds of barriers and how were they managed?

RQ5: What are the lessons learned and promising practices that can be identified in COVID-19 responses across diverse local contexts?

D7.2 proposed research design methodologies in order to conduct primary empirical research on communication responses in the 10 COVINFORM sub-national research sites and the case studies including a communication component.

Prior to determining the research design of WP7, the importance of considering “the research questions that will guide the research design to adopt, the data to collect and from whom, and data analysis and reporting” (Bryman, 2004) was acknowledged.

In D7.2, the initial set of research questions addressing communication and information policy were based on Ostrom’s Multitier framework for analysing Socio-Ecological Systems (Ostrom & Cox 2020), and the findings of Deliverable 7.1. As mentioned in D7.2, communication refers to the exchange of information among different actors and Ostrom’s framework provides variables to understand this exchange.

The D7.2 deliverable noted that all research sites would aim to address the two overarching research questions below:

- 1) How have different actors designed, delivered, and evaluated inclusive COVID-19 communication for behaviour change and addressing misinformation?
- 2) What impact have COVID-19 communication strategies and practices had on individuals from the majority population and vulnerable groups?

However, D7.2 also acknowledged that research sites may need to incorporate additional questions or tailor the questions in line with the framework and relevant target population. D7.2 includes a list of supplementary questions that were to be considered by the 10 research sites. Moreover, they were designed to act as a prompt for considering communication dimensions in the research sites. More importantly, the questions were categorised by the variables described in Ostrom’s social-ecological system (SES) framework and the relevant subunit within SES variable. These specific research questions are presented on pages 11-13 of the D7.2 deliverable. At present, the SES framework (see D7.2 for further information), which was used to form the research questions, as well as the research questions devised remain unchanged.

The research questions outlined in D7.2 were used to inform both the WP7 empirical research and for any WP3 case studies with a communication component. As the findings of the case studies will be

reported in D3.8 Final case study reports and comparative report – update M34, this deliverable focuses on the updated research design for the WP7 empirical research.

The next sections provide updates in relation to the study populations and sampling method, research participant recruitment, and data collection before moving on to summarize the feedback from COVINFORM partners on the WP7 empirical research.

3 Study Populations and Sampling Method

The analysis and findings of the expert interviews will feed into D7.7, Analysis: Communication and information – update M36. To reiterate, the D7.7 deliverable will provide an update on all five parts of D7.3, ‘Analysis: Communication and information’. The five parts are (1) Good and bad practices of COVID-19 communication strategies, (2) Communication to influence behaviour change, (3) Digital communication and exclusion, (4) Fighting malinformation, disinformation and misinformation, and (5) Representation and justice in media. Note that data for the D7.7 deliverable will be extracted from the WP7 expert interviews (to be discussed below) and the D7.1 and D7.5 deliverables.

In order to obtain the required information for D7.7, it was initially agreed that COVINFORM partners would reach out to Reporters, News Editors, Broadcasters, Media Professionals and Policy Experts for the WP7 expert interviews. Note that the latter target audience involved any government official involved in creating communication plans and crisis communication, i.e., Communication Officers/Directors. These two target audiences were specifically stated in the first interview guide created for the WP7 expert interviews. Based on COVINFORM partner feedback, however, adjustments were made to the target audience. More information on the adjustments and their justifications are presented below.

With a focus on the recruitment of Policy Experts, there was much discussion amongst consortium partners about what makes someone a “policy expert.” Ultimately, a policy expert would be anybody involved in preparing or delivering communication plans during a crisis on behalf of regional, local or national government. Following a number of discussions, and following the COVINFORM Consortium meeting in October 2022, it was agreed that it would be of greater interest to speak with those who practiced communication rather than those who planned it. Changes to the target group were made because 1) some consortium partners (e.g., SINUS) expressed previous difficulties in recruiting this profile of respondents for WP4; 2) it was difficult to identify who exactly was planning communication and; 3) The initial baseline report (D7.1) covered sufficient information about how communication was planned. Here, it is worth noting that communication was planned from more than one source, and was practiced in multiple modes, even when there was one source.

At this point of the project, the consortium decided it would be more productive to understand how people practiced communication. It would also bring more clarity to the question of what the impact of the actual communication results was, rather than simply the planning as such. Operational staff would be able to tell COVINFORM partners exactly what worked, what went wrong and why, while those who were planning have less direct insights. With this in mind, consortium partners agreed that Government Communicators would be the best target group for obtaining such information instead of Communication Experts. Thus, partners were encouraged to specifically recruit Government Communicators who were engaged in COVID-19 communication on a governmental level. Depending

on the context, COVID-19 communication on this level can range from public health to government agencies.

With regard to recruiting Reporters, News Editors, Broadcasters, and Media Professionals, modifications were also made. After careful consideration, it was agreed that the category of Journalists would be the primary focus for recruitment. The reason for this change is because consortium partners agreed that there is not much difference between a Journalist and a Broadcaster, News Editor, Reporter, and Media Professional. Following clarification with COVINFORM partners, it was understood that Journalists either work in print or broadcast. Whilst those working within the broadcast sector either work as reporters or editors, those working in print include photographers, columnists, etc.

When recruiting Journalists, the following criteria for recruitment was agreed upon: (1) Local Media/News Reporter, (2) Public Broadcaster/Service Media (e.g., in England, this would be the BBC), and (3) Biggest Media. Here, it was considered that if the Public Broadcaster/Service Media is the biggest, the second biggest Public Broadcaster/Service Media would be selected.

The reasons for selecting the three criteria are as follows:

- (1) Local Media/News Reporter: These Journalists are closer to and have better knowledge of the end users, in this case also vulnerable groups in the local society.
- (2) Public service media work under different conditions in different countries – some have commercials, others don't, some are very close to government, others are not – but they usually are regarded as quality media. In addition, public service media are mainly and usually founded by public means and are designated to formulate news for the general public on a national level.
- (3) Second biggest Public Broadcaster/Service Media: they reach the most people.

Note that WP7 leaders permitted the recruitment of editors as well because they were considered as people who were also closely involved in the communication of COVID-19 related communications, and made decisions in the editorial room.

In the D7.2 deliverable, an overview of how to establish an appropriate sample size is outlined, this remains unchanged. In the end, and as stated in the D3.6 Multi-site research design and methodological framework (update) deliverable, the COVINFORM consortium agreed that each of the WPs 4-7 would have a minimum $n=5$ expert interviews in each study site with individuals that have specific knowledge in a certain (professional) field of action (Doring, 2021).

Therefore, it was determined that each partner should conduct **$N \geq 5$** qualitative interviews with Communication Experts such as Journalists **and** Government Communicators. The ideal recruitment numbers would be the following:

- $N \geq 3$ Journalists, including editors
- $N \geq 2$ Government Communicators

A minimum of 2 experts should be recruited from each communication expert profile (i.e., at best, avoid recruiting $N=1$ Government Communicator and $N=4$ Journalists). Table 1 provides an overview of the number of interviews conducted with Government Communicators and Journalists by each research site. It also highlights the number of Government Communicators and Journalists that have been contacted about the research.

Table 1. Overview of WP7 expert interviews

Partner	Research site	Number of interviews conducted	Approximate number of Government Communicators and Journalists contacted
SU	Wales	0 (Journalists) 3 (Government Communicators)	8
SYNYO	Austria	3 (Journalists) 2 (Government Communicators)	10
UGOT	Sweden	3 (Journalists) 2 (Government Communicators)	5
UANTWERPEN	Belgium	3 (Journalists) 2 (Government Communicators)	10
SAPIENZA	Italy	3 (Journalists) 2 (Government Communicators)	7
SAMUR-PC	Spain	2 (Journalists) 0 (Government Communicators)	5
KEMEA	Greece	5 (Journalists) 0 (Government Communicators)	9
FACTOR SOCIAL	Portugal	2 (Journalists) 3 (Government Communicators)	25
TRI	England	2 (Journalists) 0 (Government Communicators)	11
SINUS	Germany	2 (Journalists) 1 (Government Communicators)	10-15

4 Recruitment

When recruiting Government Communicators and Journalists, the following criteria should have been taken into consideration:

1. Area of professional interest or content focuses predominantly on risk and crisis communication, communication planning (policy experts) and/or the COVID-19 pandemic (N≥5, minimum requirement participants, as relevant)
2. Self-identifies as female (N≥2)
3. Work is directly related to, and/or works directly with vulnerable groups (N≥5)

Solutions for recruiting vulnerable population

With a focus on Criteria 3 above, D7.2 covers the recruitment of vulnerable populations. On devising the WP7 expert interview guides, an amendment was made in terms of not recruiting Government Communicators and Journalists who work specifically with vulnerable groups. COVINFORM partners expressed that Journalists typically don't report on vulnerable groups only, whereas Government Communicators may be responsible for communication in administrative areas that predominantly

include vulnerable groups, e.g., geographical areas with migrant populations. It was agreed that partners would not restrict their recruitment to Journalists and Government Communicators who specifically report on vulnerable groups. It was also acknowledged that it is challenging to determine those at heightened vulnerability given the complex nature of increased risk during the COVID-19 pandemic. It was of more interest to understand how vulnerability was considered – if at all – on a general level. With this in mind, questions were included in the interview guide in regard to vulnerable groups.

Besides recruitment of vulnerable groups, the D7.2 deliverable also considered the social and legal risks to research participants. In addition, privacy measures were established. To date, the considerations remain the same (e.g., de-identification of data, pseudonyms being used, altering location names, healthcare service providers, facilities or organisation and unique narratives that are easily identifiable) and have been taken into account when conducting interviews.

Informed Consent

Following the informed consent process outlined in D7.2, prior to interviews, research participants are provided with an information sheet. The information sheet outlines key information about the research, the use of participants data, the advantages and risks of participating, the participants rights, and contact details for the project coordinator and researcher conducting the interview. Once research participants have read, understood, and confirmed that they want to proceed with the research, they complete and sign an informed consent form.

5 Data collection

As outlined in D3.2, the main research method used for WPs 4-7 is semi-structured interviews. Two separate interview guides were created to collect data during the WP7 expert interviews. One guide was created for Government Communicators, and another guide was created for Journalists due to the different nature of their roles. The interview guides and interview questions created for the WP7 expert interviews are available in annexes 1 and 2 and have parallels with the proposed questions presented in the D7.2 deliverable. Examples of similar themes covered in D7.2 and the expert interview guides include risk and crisis communication, targeted communication, digital access to COVID-19 communication, trust of COVID-19 communication, and misinformation.

To ensure that the right questions were being asked to both target groups, consortium partners were encouraged to provide feedback on the initial set of guides that were created and distributed. The guides were re-drafted, and the final set of questions incorporated were those advised by partners. The points below are examples of some of the feedback and key areas the consortium wanted the guide to include.

Government Communicators Interview Guide

1. Incorporate a question that focused on the difference in the communication of the COVID-19 pandemic from other crises and in what way.
2. Being clear when using the word “communication.” Following feedback, certain partners felt as if the consortium had a very academic view of what the term entails, which may have not translated to Government Communicators’ understanding of “communication.” Given these circumstances, the WP7 leaders made sure to frame any question relating to communication as “communicating information about COVID-19.”

3. The need to explore “why” and “how,” instead of just “what.” It was acknowledged that policy experts (now changed to Government Communicators) are responsible for communicating to the public. More than knowing what they communicated, consortium partners felt that the consortium have a window to better understand what led them to say x and y at a given point of time. Did Government Communicators, for example, consider peoples’ fears, perceptions, needs, wants, and vulnerable situations? Moreover, did Government Communicators consider already known risk and crisis communication principles?
4. The need to consider the aspect of vulnerability and which groups were considered to be particularly vulnerable within the context of COVID-19. This was considered because the responses would have helped the consortium understand whether the needs of these people were considered in the communication strategy efforts the respondent worked on.
5. During the project, consortium partners came to the realisation that many health and policy experts failed to communicate according to the main principles stated in risk and crisis communication literature. With this in mind, consortium partners felt it was crucial to better understand how these experts perceive risk and crisis communication itself.

Journalist Interview Guide

1. The strategies of most news media are to get the most important news published as soon as possible, and preferably before the most important competitors – no matter the information being reported. Consortium partners felt it was important to ask whether there were any difficulties in reporting on COVID-19, such as understanding and transmitting information based on scientific findings. Here, we were also interested to know whether special scientific journalists formed part of the editorial staff and how assignments were divided between reporters with different competences and skills.
2. Partner feedback highlighted the importance of including a question about how Journalists tried to bridge the gap between government communication and the public. In addition to this, consortium partners felt it was important to ask when they chose to amplify what the government were saying, and at what point.

Incorporating the feedback from partners, the interview guides were finalised prior to the interviews. During the interviews, researchers made handwritten notes and with the research participants consent, interviews were audio recorded and transcribed for analysis.

Before moving on to cover data analysis, the next section will summarize partners feedback on the WP7 research.

6 Methodological reflections

This section will specifically focus on methodological reflections for the WP7 expert interviews. To understand the consortium’s overall experience of conducting the WP7 empirical research with Journalists and Government Communicators, a survey was created and shared with partners. Excluding Trilateral Research (creator of the WP7 survey), 10 responses were received. Below, the questions included in the survey and an overview of the responses and experiences of all partners involved in the interviews has been highlighted.

Q1. How did you recruit Journalists? Please describe the approaches used.

Overall, consortium partners recruited Journalists via existing contacts, by email, or by using both approaches.

Q2. How did you recruit Government Communicators? Please describe the approaches used.

When recruiting Government Communicators, consortium partners followed the same approach as above with Journalists. Only two partners were unsuccessful with recruitment. In one country, the partner was unable to recruit Government Communicators because officials outlined how they are currently responding to a Public Enquiry on COVID, and must be careful not to compromise that activity. To determine whether the situation had changed, the Government Communicator was contacted one final time in March 2023. They remained unavailable to participate.

Q3. What challenges and difficulties did you face when recruiting Journalists and Government Communicators to participate in the research? Please comment on both experiences.

Consortium partners commented on the following challenges and difficulties:

- 1) Availability. For example, one partner explained that it took more than two months between initial agreement to interview and the actual interview in the case of Government Officials. Another respondent also noted difficulties in recruiting Journalists because of availability constraints;
- 2) Length of interview. One partner said that one Journalist turned down an interview because it was too long (e.g., 60 minutes);
- 3) Slow or no responses;
- 4) No interest in taking part;
- 5) Difficulty accessing senior Government Communicators;
- 6) Time constraints;
- 7) Conflicting research. For example, being unable to participate in the COVINFORM research because of other research activities;
- 8) Limited COVID-19/Health reporting knowledge. For example, with Journalists, some local press outlets had staff who reported exclusively or mainly on COVID-19-related (or even health-related) matters; thus, some potential research participants felt underqualified;

Q4. If you experienced difficulties with recruitment, what measures or different approaches did you take to secure the interviews? Please specify any differences in approaches for Journalists and Government Communicators

Whilst most respondents did not have anything to say about measures implemented to secure the missing interviews, four measures were highlighted by partners. They include the following:

- 1) Explaining time sensitivity of the interview and offering research assistance, to make the approach collaborative instead of extractive;
- 2) Sending frequent follow up emails to Government Communicators in different departments and at different levels. As for Journalists, measures involved a Journalist interviewed linking the interviewer with other Journalists;
- 3) Using main points of contact for referrals.
- 4) Careful explanation of the project aims and ethics/data protection measures.

Q5. What challenges and difficulties did you face when conducting the research? Please specify whether these challenges relate to conducting research with Journalists, Government Communicators, or both.

- 1) Government Communicator interviews were guarded and stuck strongly to policies. It was difficult to get Government Communicators to speak their mind. For some of the partners, this also applied to Journalists being interviewed;
- 2) At times, it would be difficult to get answers to some of the questions;
- 3) No time for questions or more critical self-reflection;
- 4) Topic guide too wide-ranging to be worked through in 60 minutes.

Q6. What did you do to overcome the challenges and difficulties?

Key adjustments implemented to overcome challenges and difficulties for the WP7 expert interviews include:

- 1) Employing techniques of creating trust and gently pointing out how some policies or underpinnings could lead to problematic outcomes;
- 2) Following the flow of information provided by interlocutors, instead of sticking too closely to the interview guide. This way, it was possible to adapt the questions if necessary;
- 3) Contacting interviewees who were interviewed one year earlier, to see if they could answer the updated questions relevant to the COVID-19 pandemic;
- 4) Making sure to ask critical questions to both Government Communicators and Journalists;
- 5) Reformulating the questions pertaining vulnerable populations and giving examples that were known to have happened (e.g., some social media from official government and health authorities accounts posting content targeting youth and the elderly). In addition, redundant questions were avoided. Alternatively, questions were skipped, especially those which caused discomfort for the interviewee or had already been answered previously;
- 6) Shortening sections about which participants had little to say;
- 7) Asking follow-up questions on areas about which certain participants were eager to share their opinions.

Q7. What worked well in organising and conducting the research?

Several comments were raised, and the following points were highlighted:

- 1) Demonstrating determination to the interviewees' point of view and not delivering scathing critique or pointing fingers at people or institutions;
- 2) Smooth recruitment and conduction of interviews;
- 3) Interviews finishing at a timely manner and determination to answer questions to the best of the interviewee's ability;
- 4) Recruiting candidates and conducting interviews in a short time span;
- 5) Willingness to share experiences;
- 6) Productive conversations due to having personal contacts;
- 7) Interviewers and fieldwork coordinators having extensive experience working together.

Q8. What feedback, if any, did you receive from the interviewees?

The overall feedback received from the interviewees has been positive. Comments include:

- 1) Interviewees enjoying the intellectual nature of the interviews, which made them think in a good way;
- 2) Interest in the project and its results. Interviewees asked to be informed once they had first-hand insights;
- 3) Interviewees being talkative and reflective. Most of the interviews that were conducted lasted longer than scheduled;
- 4) Well-structured questionnaire, whereby the sub-questions already included didn't have to be asked. Interviewees naturally addressed the questions by themselves;
- 5) Positive and covering the most important topics

Q9. What, if any, ethical issues occurred that were not considered before the field research?

The only ethical issues that occurred, out of all the responses received, was confidentiality. People working for ministries, for example, could not answer freely. The same applied to Journalists as some newspapers are closely affiliated with political ideologies, which means they have more or less contact to some politicians.

Q10. In a few words, how would you describe your experience conducting WP7 expert interviews?

Most partners agreed that the interviews conducted with Journalists and Government Communicators were “insightful.” Other words, particularly positive terminology, used to describe the interviews include:

- 1) Positive
- 2) Interesting
- 3) Stimulating
- 4) Forthcoming
- 5) Rich
- 6) Enriching
- 7) Rewarding
- 8) Productive
- 9) Enjoyable
- 10) Thought-provoking
- 11) Inspiring

Other comments received include some interviews being controversial, way off in terms of alignment of intentions and policy formation, and taking a lot of effort, patience and persistence.

Q11. Why have you selected these words to describe your experience?

Partners expressed that by conducting the interviews it offered them additional insights that could not be drawn from researching communication policies or strategies.

“The interviews did provide some information that we could not find out through our back research but somewhat suspected. It was also really fascinating to hear what went on in the ministry of health and in newsrooms during the lockdowns and how people managed”

This enriched the evidence that was collated in the desk-based research and reported in D7.1 Baseline report: Communication and information. Particularly in the context of communication with most vulnerable members of society.

“Shows fundamental discrepancies in understanding and acting on vulnerability and shows how people in charge see the world”

The interviewers also gained insights as to how communication professionals were required to change their typical communication practices and adapt their roles and strategies as the pandemic changed overtime.

“I chose these words because it was interesting to see how the COVID-19 pandemic had an impact on the change of roles and how COVID-19 information should have been communicated during a time when misinformation and disinformation was rapidly growing”

Q12. From what you can remember, how engaged would you say the Journalists and Government Communicators were when interviewed?

Overall, most of the interviewees (both Journalists and Government Communicators) were engaged in the interviews. Only a few partners reported disengagement amongst Journalists and Government Communicators. Journalist disengagement concerned being wary of disclosing too much information, for example.

Q13. Knowing what you know now, what would you do differently when collecting data for the WP7 expert interviews?

Some of the key takeaways here include:

- 1) Approaching interviewees sooner with more clarifying language to explain that partners are not seeking to blame anyone;

- 2) In Belgium, for example, it was noted that those carrying out the interviews felt they could have tried harder to conduct interviews with someone from the Brussels or Wallonian government, and not just Flemish speaking;
- 3) The eligible sample of interviewees should perhaps not be so narrow as a way to overcome recruiting challenges;
- 4) Taking advantage of social media platforms and discuss the benefits of taking part in the research;
- 5) A shorter topic guide, with a tighter and more explicit connection to the specific research questions identified on the project and WP levels. This is not meant as a point of criticism, as the revised research questions had not been finalised by the time the topic guide was written.

Q14. What are your plans for scheduling and/or conducting the remaining interviews for WP7?

Most interviews have been completed. For interviews not yet complete, especially with Journalists, partners have interviews either scheduled until the end of February or resorted to researching Journalists who published articles about the COVID-19 pandemic. Note that the eligible criteria still apply. Other strategies for Journalist recruitment include waiting for a press release that partners wrote for the local health board as a reason to get in touch with Journalists. According to the partners, this would have sparked interest in the COVINFORM project, and strengthen participation in an interview. Despite the press release going live, however, little interest was garnered. Following up with the potential interviewees has helped.

Q15. Could you reflect on the impact of your own position during the data collection? (“researcher positionality”)

Partners raised the following reflections:

1. When discussing definitions and understandings of vulnerability beyond the biological and clinical, interviewees reflected on what it was that made the lockdowns, travel restrictions, and vaccinations difficult. Some would say that they were so glad they had spent lockdowns with family or a partner etc and to push them a little on elaborating on what made it good and not so good, I’d share my experiences of living alone.... Same goes with experiencing language issues (even though it had been a while for me and interviewer X) and language culture that sometimes confused non-native speakers and that are not remarked on by native speakers. British people, for example, would not fully understand how language was another thing to negotiate in figuring out what was expected of people living in Wales – both in following the rules and getting tested and vaccinated. As immigrants with other-than-English mother tongues ourselves, interviewer X and I recognised the difficulty in understanding what’s precisely meant in English, as sentences and terms often don’t have exact translations, and from knowing how the culture of the English language (expressions and local vernacular) as used in Wales and Swansea in government and healthcare settings can feel foreign and difficult to understand. I used all these positions and experiences to relate to interviewees or push them to think beyond their Welsh/British understanding of vulnerability in the pandemic context...”
2. With a particular focus on Journalist interviews, having prior knowledge about the process, originating from the country, and some internal knowledge about the country’s Public Broadcaster helped a lot. This knowledge allowed the Journalists to provide additional information when the recording device was turned off. In sum, however, researcher positionality didn’t influence the interviews too much;
3. Being aware that since some of the interviewees belong to the same network as the interviewers, there was already pre-understanding of the working conditions;
4. Researcher positionality was less of an issue with the expert interviews, compared to interviews with vulnerable populations. The only point worth mentioning is social-desirability

bias, e.g., Government Communicators and Journalists hoping to answer questions by overreporting ‘good’ policies or work they did during the pandemic;

5. Possessing a certain professional role, for example, helped with the recruitment and willingness to take part in the interviews;
6. Making sure personal views of the COVID-19 pandemic did not influence the way interviews were conducted;
7. Having a Journalism background helped with recruitment and interest;
8. Positionality of researchers and “expert” research participants articulated in D6.2 (Section 6.2) also apply to WP7, insofar as the interviewees are established professionals within their fields of practice. Generally, the power differentials between researchers and participants in the context of expert interviews are less significant than between researchers and, for example, representatives of vulnerable populations. The researchers found this to be the case during the data collection at hand. Insofar, as both the researchers and the participants were experts in the field of communication (albeit within different sub-fields), the interviews sometimes attained a more conversational than interrogative character. This was mostly positive from the perspective of both the researchers and the participants.

7 Data Analysis

As stated in the D7.2 deliverable, researchers must be able to identify a suitable approach to data analysis depending on the research process conducted. The different analysis approaches include:

- 1) Frameworks approaches and thematic analysis
- 2) Interpretative approaches and grounded theory

For further information on each of the approaches, please refer to D7.2.

For the D7.3 deliverable, the first iteration of the analysis of communication and information, an explorative approach was adopted. D7.3, specifically focused on (1) the analysis of memes, public health campaigns, and government communication strategies. This involved WP leaders identifying themes and topics used in the information campaigns through manual inductive coding in conducting a content analysis. The analysis followed the logic of Panofsky’s (1962) iconographic-iconological method (see also Muller 2011), identifying and categorising themes per country as well as overarching themes and stylistic elements. To learn more about the details of this method, please refer to page 14 of D7.3.

Following the analysis, the findings were translated into lessons learned and guidelines were presented in Deliverable D7.4 Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information, and misinformation. The synthesis and interpretation of findings of the previous tasks of WP7 were based on the theoretical framework established in WPs 2 and 3, i.e., Complex Systems Theory (Ostrom 2007). This was corresponded with a theoretical reflection on risk and crisis communication, especially the Risk Governance Framework (IRGC, 2017), which outlines questions to address when developing communication, and the Protective Action Decision Model (PADM) (Lindell & Perry 2012). Relating these theoretical models/frameworks to the Ostrom (2007) Systems Model, WP7 leaders visualised how Ostrom’s 2007 model is an appropriate and relevant theoretical framework to compare the communication approaches of the 10 COVINFORM countries. In the D7.4 deliverable, WP7 leaders proposed an approach that analyses COVID-19 risk and crisis communication via the lens of complex adaptive system theory. According to WP7 leaders, the approach proved to be useful in terms of comprehending the relationships between various components influencing risk and crisis communication and will be applied to the D7.7, Analysis: Communication and information due in M34 (June 2023). The same analysis approach will be applied to Dx.7 series for WP4-6 also. This will enable the COVINFORM project to discuss and compare findings across WPs.

8 Conclusions

This report presents an update of the research design and methods that have been applied in the empirical research and case study research relating to WP7, Information and Communication. To address the overarching research questions, the consortium engaged in numerous discussions to tailor research guides for those involved in practicing communication related to COVID-19. The study participants include Communication Experts, i.e. Journalists and Government Communicators. Consortium partners provided feedback on the challenges faced during recruitment, the semi-structured interviews and also valued insights regarding the conduct of the interviews. The findings from the expert interviews will be presented in D7.7, Analysis: Communication and information due in M34 (June 2023), following the same framework analysis as previously described in D3.2, Design research activities per case study'. This will be accompanied by resulting short country reports from each target country involved. Following this, the breath of evidence collated under WP7 will be synthesised and presented with clear recommendations to policy makers in respect to communication practices during crisis situations. This will be reported in D7.8, Synthesis and lessons learnt on communication, information and misinformation – update M35 (July 2023).

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Annex 1

Interview guide for Government Communicators

Background

Can you tell me about your role and since when have you been working in this position? (job title, organisation, daily tasks, responsibilities).

Were you involved in the planning of COVID-19 communication and/or did you act as a communicator?

Can you tell me about the role of your institution in the pandemic response of your country?

Introduction/warm-up questions

Since the initial pandemic outbreak, what does a typical workday look like for you? Could you describe how the COVID-19 pandemic changed your role or procedures? Prompt: e.g., changes in responsibilities, tasks, decision-making processes, communication practices or approaches.

What would you say are the main aspects to consider when communicating about risk to the general public?

Main questions (Government Communicators)

How was COVID-19 risk communication structured, managed and practised in your institution and in particular by yourself?

- a. Where would you get the information from that you used for further communication?
- b. How did you decide what to communicate and what not?
- c. How did you decide how to communicate about COVID-19 and the COVID-19 responses?
- d. In your organisation, what different roles did key members of staff have in communicating information about COVID-19? Please state the different actors involved in communicating COVID-19 communication.

How was risk communication coordinated across different organisations at either the national, regional and/or local level?

Can you describe your organisation's COVID-19 risk communication strategy?

- a. Would you say there was anything different regarding COVID-19 communication in comparison to other crises?
- b. What did you want to achieve with the strategy (i.e., what were the goals?) For example, did COVID-19 communication seek to increase knowledge, influence behaviour, build trust, etc?
- c. Who did you target with the strategy?

In your organisation, was there targeted communication directed towards specific groups of people?

- a. If so, how was it tailored and achieved?
- b. Which groups of people were taken into consideration?
- c. How did you gather insights on the communities' information needs?
- d. How were other cross-cultural differences addressed, if at all?
- e. How did your organisation also overcome specific barriers such as individuals' lack of access to technology?

In your organisation, did you have a pre-existing risk communication plan?

- a. Did your organisation use the plan(s) and were the plan(s) appropriate for use during the COVID-19 pandemic? If not, why were they not appropriate?
- b. How were they adapted to suit the nature of the COVID-19 pandemic?
- c. Could you please describe how and why COVID-19 risk communication changed over time?

With conflicting information available, how did you or your colleagues make sure that the information was consistent?**In your organisation, which groups do you consider particularly vulnerable in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic?**

- a. In your organisation, what considerations of addressing vulnerable groups were identified?
- b. How did you reflect on the experiences and impact of COVID-19 on different groups in your communication?

How did you assess/evaluate the effectiveness of your organisation's COVID-19 communication?

- a. In engaging with the public?
- b. In engaging with vulnerable/hard-to-reach communities?
- c. In influencing behaviour change?
- d. In addressing false information? What impact did this have?
- e. What other impacts did the COVID-19 communication have? For example, change in public opinion and ways in which public trust has changed throughout the pandemic?

How did your organisation/what was your role in addressing misinformation?

- a. What impact did this response have?

In your organisation, what lessons were learnt in communicating about COVID-19?

- a. What overall challenges were faced in communicating about COVID-19? And how did you address these challenges?
- b. If there was another pandemic, what would you do differently in terms of communication?

Is there anything else that you would like to share about communicating with vulnerable groups during the pandemic?

Is there anything you'd like to raise that we have not covered during this interview?

Annex 2

Interview guide for Journalists

Background

Can you tell me about your role? (job title, organisation, daily tasks, responsibilities).

Introduction/warm-up questions

How did the COVID-19 pandemic change the focus of your work?

- d. What did you consider your responsibility in the reporting of COVID-19?
- e. If applicable, why were you investigating and reporting on a specific topic during the pandemic?

Main questions (journalists)

In your organisation, what different roles did you and your colleagues have in reporting information about COVID-19? Please briefly state the different actors involved in communicating COVID-19 within your organisation.

Can you describe your organisation's COVID-19 reporting approach?

- a. What did you consider your responsibility in the reporting of COVID-19?
- b. Was there anything different regarding COVID-19 communication in comparison to other crises?
- c. Where did your organisation feel it was important to amplify specific messages (e.g., vaccination campaigns) or specific criticisms?
- d. Besides the usual channels you use to publish your stories, what other communication platforms did you use to publish your stories?
- e. How did it change throughout the pandemic?
- f. How did you follow the organisation's strategy?
- g. Did you face any difficulties in reporting on COVID-19, such as understanding and transmitting information based on specific findings?
- h. Were there special science journalists on the editorial staff to help report the findings?
- i. How were the assignments divided between reporters with different competences and skills?

In your organisation, what information or resources did you use to make decisions about COVID-19 reporting? Please also explain how you accessed such information.

- a. How did you know the information you were using to report on COVID-19 could be trusted?

How did your organisation communicate with your usual audience?

- a. Did you receive any feedback from your usual audience (e.g., letters to the editor, live feeds) and did you act on any of the feedback?
- b. How did your organisation engage with different communities?
- c. Did your organisation consider it to be a responsibility to communicate with different communities?
- d. If so, what did your organisation do to make sure that the information was inclusive and accessible to different communities? (e.g., was information tailored (e.g., translation) to meet the needs of different groups?)
- e. How did you gather insights on the communities' information needs?
- f. How were other cross-cultural differences addressed, if at all?
- g. How did your or other organisations overcome barriers such as user lack of access to technology?

In your organisation, what considerations of addressing vulnerable groups were identified?

- a. How did you reflect on the experiences and impact of COVID-19 on different groups in your communication? OR Please talk me through the work your organisation engaged in to represent different communities (especially vulnerable/hard-to-reach groups) in the media and if applicable, how the public respond to such representations.

What were your thoughts on COVID-19 communication by the government?

- a. How did you try to bridge the gap between government communication and the public?
- b. How transparent would you say government COVID-19 communication was? Please elaborate.
- c. Please tell me about any prominent COVID-19 reporting that stood out to you and why?
- d. How did government COVID-19 communication influence your trust in the government? Please elaborate.
- e. Please comment on how COVID-19 communication differed from previous pandemic communication?

In comparison to government COVID-19 communication, how did you assess/evaluate the effectiveness of the information about COVID-19 that you reported on?

- a. What did you observe in terms of specific reactions from the public regarding your reporting of the COVID-19 pandemic?
- b. When did you choose to amplify what the government was saying and at what point did you start to publish criticism? What information did the government provide that you started to publish? Which information was not published? And what kind of information was published?

If you consider COVID-19 reporting from different actors (i.e., government bodies or public health bodies, experts), how did you or your colleagues make sure that the information was consistent?

- a. As information about COVID-19 was constantly changing, did you feel this was problematic (e.g., in terms of credibility)? If so, why?

How did your organisation/what was your role in addressing misinformation?

- a. What impact did this response have?

In your organisation, what lessons were learnt in reporting about COVID-19?

- a. What challenges can you comment on in relation to communicating about COVID-19? And how did you address these challenges?
- b. If applicable, what additional support (e.g., training)/resources would have helped you when communicating COVID-19?
- c. If there was another pandemic, what would you do differently in terms of communication?

13. Is there anything else you'd like to raise that we have not covered during this interview?